

FOOD MARKETING AND CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR: A SOCIOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: The changing pattern of food culture and lifestyle among people, characterized by increased reliance on convenience foods and eating out, has created a vacuum for food companies to fill through marketing. This study thereby aimed to investigate the impact of food marketing on consumer's behaviour in Nsukka LGA, Enugu State. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design. A total of 600 respondents aged 18 years and above, and residing in Nsukka were selected for the study. A multistage sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents. The data obtained were sorted, assembled, coded, and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 22). Findings from the study revealed that the influence of food marketing on consumers' purchasing behaviour is very high among the respondents in Nsukka LGA. The study further revealed that price, packaging and labeling were significant factors influencing consumer's food purchasing behaviour. The study also revealed that food marketing has significant impact towards buying of unhealthy food. More so, the study established a strong association between active social media use and influence of food marketing. Based on these findings, the study primarily recommended that Nigerian government and lawmakers should establish and enforce regulations to restrict the marketing of unhealthy food products, particularly to vulnerable population such as children and adolescents.

Keywords: Marketing, Consumer, Consumer Behaviour, Food, Customers

Introduction:

Marketing has become an important tool for businesses to connect with customers and influence what they buy. According to Corporate Finance Institute (CFI; 2022), marketing refers to business activities associated with communicating, advertising, delivering, or selling products or services to customers. The goal of marketing is to draw the consumers' attention to the company's products, and maintaining relationship with them. As marketing has become more advanced, it is now a priority for the success of any business, from small-scale, independent farms to multinational food manufacturers.

Food, which falls under one of the four types of consumer products, is one of the most highly marketed products in the world (Harris et al., 2020). Food marketing refers to "any communication designed to increase recognition, appeal and/or consumption of specific food products, brands and services (Smith et al., 2019). According to

Tsochantaridou et al. (2023), food marketing takes many forms and can involve building relationships with customers, raising brand awareness, developing new products, and promoting them through advertising, all with the goal of promoting sales. Over the past few decades, the food industry has become one of the most lucrative and competitive sectors of the global economy. With the rise of globalization and digital technologies, food manufacturers and retailers have developed sophisticated marketing strategies to promote their products and increase their market share. As a result, food marketing has become an omnipresent and ubiquitous presence in the society, shaping the way people eat, drink, and think about food (Arnolds, 2023).

Globally, the food and beverages market size has grown strongly in recent years, from \$6576.96 billion in 2023 to \$7000.88 billion in 2024 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.4% (Business Research Company, 2024). The growth in the historic period can be attributed to strong economic growth in emerging markets, and increasing internet penetration and advertisement (Business Research Company, 2024). For instance, according to the official statistics from the United States (US) Bureau of Labour Statistics (2022) Americans spend around 12.5% of their income buying food. This includes both groceries and eating out at restaurants. Germany, with its large population of over 83 million, boasts a lucrative food and beverage market. With addition of delivery services and technological advancements, online consumers are expected to grow from 62.4 million in 2020 to 68.4 million by 2025, driving the growth of Germany's food service market (Fortune Business Insight, 2024). In India, the ready-to-eat food industry has experienced impressive growth, driven by changing consumer lifestyles, urbanization, and the increasing demand for convenience. The evolving lifestyles and preferences of consumers have paved the way for the remarkable success of the food industry (Bhalerao, 2023).

Food plays a vital role in African culture and is deeply rooted in tradition and community and food companies have become increasingly aware of the vast potential in Africa's burgeoning consumer market. The continent, now home to more than 1.4 billion people, is estimated to reach 4.6 billion by 2100 (Galah, 2024). More and more Africans are entering the consumer class, with tens of millions emerging from poverty in recent years. With a diverse range of dishes across the continent, food marketing in Africa has become increasingly important for businesses to reach consumers with companies using digital platforms, outdoor advertisement, social media, and influencer partnerships to reach a growing middle class with increasing disposable income (Badiane et al., 2023; Mkumbo & Mbise, 2022). In Ghana, Amevinya et al. (2023) found that the most advertised food product was sugar-sweetened drinks. More so, Different promotional techniques deployed included the use of claim pronouncement, promotional characters, emotional appeal, premium offer, and price promotion. In South Africa, discount offers are a major driver of consumer behaviour towards food purchase. As noted by Coggin (2023), 97% of South African consumers use their local newspaper to plan their purchases and research discount buys. Nigeria, as an emerging market, has gained attention in global food industry with many local and international food companies competing for consumers' attentions (Oluyemi, 2023). The World Trade Organisation (WTO; 2023) ranked Nigeria as the largest food market in Africa, with significant investment in the local industry and a high level of imports. The food and beverage sector is estimated to contribute 22.5% of the manufacturing industry value, and 4.6% of the country's GDP. More so, Nigerians spend an average of 73% of their income on food and

beverages products, however given the choice, a vast majority of Nigerian consumers will opt for food and beverages products made outside of the country (Shama, 2021). Furthermore, the high demand for processed and fast foods in Nigeria is closely linked to effective food marketing strategies employed by both local and multinational companies, which have successfully created a strong desire for convenient and affordable options among Nigerian consumers (Adebowale et al., 2023). Meanwhile, Mekonnen et al. (2022) observed that these food products are designed to be extremely palatable and convenient, are often sold in large portion sizes. For instance, In Imo State, a study by Oguizu and Mbakwe (2023) found that majority (70.7%) of the respondents consumed ultra-processed foods/drinks and most of them consumed it because it was always available. In Enugu, Agbaeze et al. (2017) identified factors such as availability of product, packaging, quality of product, brand loyalty and promotion all affected customer patronage towards beverage food drinks. In addition, sales promotion through rebates, free trial and free gifts is one significant tool marketing companies are using to influence consumer's behaviour in Abuja (Orji et al., 2020).

Many factors have been disclosed to be affecting consumer's behaviour and perception towards food marketing. For instance, anecdotal evidence from Ghana shows that the consumption of fast food is considered an indicator of social status (Searcey & Richtel 2017). Also, Kappes et al. (2021) identified financial capacity as influencing factor as they noted that food choices may be determined by the consumer's purchasing power. In broader perspective, Chen and Antonelli (2020) identified five main factors: food-internal factors (sensory and perceptual features), food-external factors (information, social environment, and physical environment), personal-state factors (biological features and physiological needs, psychological components, habits, and experiences), cognitive factors (knowledge and skills, attitude, liking and preference, anticipated consequences, and personal identity), and sociocultural factors (culture, economic variables, and political elements). Together, these factors form the foundation of the science of food choice, which seeks to understand the complex reasons behind individuals' eating habits and answer fundamental questions about what, how, and why people eat the way they do (Blake et al 2021)

The Nigerian government has implemented various interventions to regulate product and food marketing and protect consumers from misleading and deceptive practices. The Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission (FCCPC) was established in 2019 to oversee consumer protection and regulate marketing practices. The commission has issued guidelines and regulations for advertising and marketing, requiring companies to promote fair business practices and to safeguard the interests of consumers (FCCPC, 2020). Additionally, the Nigerian Food and Drug Administration (NAFDAC) regulates food marketing and ensures that food products are safe for consumption, labeling and advertising are accurate, and compliance with standards and regulations is enforced. NAFDAC also conducts regular inspections and monitoring of food products to prevent the sale of harmful or adulterated products (Ukwueze, 2019). Furthermore, the Consumer Protection Council (CPC) has been actively involved in enforcing consumer rights, investigating complaints, and imposing sanctions on companies that violate consumer rights. The government has also established the Advertising Practitioners Council of Nigeria (APCON) to regulate advertising practices, and check all forms of abuses such as misleading statements, spurious

testimonials, visual and verbal exaggerations, and misleading offers (Ajibade, 2020). These interventions demonstrate the Nigerian government's commitment to protecting consumers and promoting fair marketing practices in the country. However, lack of supervision, corruption and incompetence have made these agencies ineffective to tackle harmful marketing.

The positive and negative impact of food marketing on the behaviour of consumers is of interests to sociologists. Sociology as a social science discipline is the study of society, social interactions, and the structures that shape our behaviour and relationships (Murcott, 2019). The sociological approach focuses on marketing strategies and techniques and its influence on food choices, dietary habits, and overall health outcomes of people. Sociologists study how food marketing campaigns can promote cultural norms around food consumption, such as promoting fast food as a convenient and affordable option for busy individuals (Creswell, 2020). These marketing tactics can also contribute to the normalization of unhealthy eating habits and the rise of food-related health issues like obesity and diabetes in certain communities. Furthermore, food marketing can reflect and perpetuate societal attitudes towards body image and food as a status symbol, contributing to harmful patterns of consumption and eating disorders (Luick, 2020).

The changing pattern of food culture and lifestyle among people, characterized by increased reliance on convenience foods and eating out, has created a vacuum for food companies to fill through marketing. With a market highly saturated with food promotion and advertisement, consumers are increasingly swayed by marketing tactics employed by food companies to promote their products as quick, affordable, and easy options for meals. Food marketing through media such as television and advergaming has been shown to impact eating and related behaviours such as purchasing (Russell et al., 2019; Finlay et al., 2022). However, little has been shown on the overall impact on consumers as well as factors driving food decisions. More so, while studies on food marketing have concentrated on urban areas in many parts of the world, consumer's rural areas such as Nsukka Local Government area in Enugu State, Nigeria, have not received adequate attention.

The specific objectives of the study were: a) To know if food marketing influences consumers' behaviour in Nsukka LGA; (b) To find out the level of food marketing in influencing consumers' behaviour in Nsukka LGA (c) To investigate the factors that influence consumers' behaviours toward food marketing in Nsukka LGA; (d) To examine the impacts of food marketing on behaviour of consumers in purchasing unhealthy food in Nsukka LGA and (e) To ascertain the measures and policies promoting and protecting consumer's rights and wellbeing in food marketing in Nsukka LGA.

The theory of reasoned action was used as the theoretical orientation. The theory of reasoned action states that the attitude and subjective norms work together to produce intention, which ultimately leads to behaviour. While the basis of this theory is that intention precedes behaviour, other factors may intervene before the intention is realised. A key aspect of the theory is that it predicts that individuals will act in a way that is consistent with their attitudes and subjective norms. Therefore, if an individual's attitude towards a behaviour is positive, they are more likely to engage in that behaviour, and if an individual's subjective norm is negative, they are less likely to engage in that behaviour.

The theory of reasoned action has been applied and researched in many health-related behaviours such as addictive behaviours (smoking, alcoholism, and gambling), breakfast and fast food consumption. For example, Hosseini et al. (2015) carried out a study to test whether the Theory of Reasoned Action would increase individuals' likelihood of consuming breakfast, and found that participants were more likely to consume breakfast if they believed that those around them were consuming breakfast and that these people around them would want them to consume breakfast. Also a study by Kumar et al. (2022) observed that that environmental concern as a result of subjective norm of consumers is the strongest predictor of Attitude (AA); willingness to Purchase (WP); and Actual Buying Behaviour (ABB) in organic food purchase. Whereas Price Perception (PP) is the least influencing factor.

Fishbein and Ajzen (1980) promote the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) as a paramount framework for predicting human behaviour related to food choices. The TRA provides invaluable insights into the expected outcomes of a particular behaviour, shedding light on the cognitive processes underlying consumer decision-making. Specifically, this theory has been chosen because it emphasizes the significance of attitude towards food choices, encompassing personal beliefs and evaluations; the influence of subjective norms; including social pressures and perceived expectations from others and the intentional nature of behaviour; recognizing that consumers make deliberate decisions based on available information. By applying the TRA, this study aims to explore how food marketing strategies shape consumer attitudes, subjective norms, and subsequent behavioural intentions.

Study Area and Setting:

The study area was Enugu State Southeastern Nigeria. The name of the State is derived from its capital city - "Enugwu" - meaning "top of the hill". Enugu State comprises social groups that are substantially mixed up with a good number of the youth due to the presence of various higher institutions in the State including the University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN) where the study was conducted. The youth are known to be easily influenced by what they see or hear especially this era of social media and Nsukka LGA harbours quit a number of the youth population; therefore, conducting a study on food marketing among them is very important and finding out if it affects their consumer behaviour paramount.

Design and Sampling Techniques:

The study employed a cross-sectional survey; employing the simple random sampling technique. It was the most straightforward probability sampling strategy. Simple random sampling is a type of probability sampling in which the researchers randomly selects a subset of participants from a population (a sample for study from a larger group (a population). In Nsukka L.G.A, there were 12 communities namely; Alor Uno, Anuka, Ede Oballa, Edem, Eha-Alumona, Ibagwa Ani, Lejja, Nsukka, Obimo, Okpuje, Okutu and Opi. Each member of the population had an equal chance of being selected. In adopting simple random sampling technique, a random number of communities was generated by drawing names from a hat by balloting and randomly picking three communities, which were; Nsukka, Ibagwa-Ani and Obukpa in Nsukka L.G.A. To get to the 600 respondents which was the sample size for the study; 200 questionnaires were assigned to each of these three communities. Further, the researchers used the

convenience sampling method to select respondents (a male and a female at an equal ratio) who were willing and available to participate in the study. Therefore, 100 males and 100 females filled the questionnaire in each community visited.

Data Collection:

The major and only instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. The questionnaires schedule contained open-ended and closed-ended questions and structured in a way that the respondent only ticked appropriately in the boxes provided. The questionnaire was divided into two sections; sections A and B. The A section covered the respondents' demographic information while the B section focused on the substantive questions relevant to the study. It was also used to test the hypotheses.

The questionnaire was self-administered to respondents in their various communities. Since the researchers had three communities to visit, the administration of questionnaire lasted for a period of three weeks; assigning a week to each community visited. Prior to the administration of the questionnaires, the researchers sought and got the approval and consent of the respondents as well as assured them of their confidentiality and anonymity. This study employed the simple random sampling technique. It was the most straightforward probability sampling strategy. Simple random sampling is a type of probability sampling in which the researcher randomly selects a subset of participants from a population (a sample for study from a larger group (a population). In Nsukka L.G.A, there are 12 communities namely; Alor Uno, Anuka, Ede Oballa, Edem, Eha-Alumona, Ibagwa Ani, Lejja, Nsukka, Obimo, Okpuje, Okutu and Opi. Each member of the population had an equal chance of being selected. In adopting simple random sampling technique, a random number of communities was generated by drawing names from a bowl by balloting and picking three communities, which were; Nsukka, Ibagwa Ani and Obukpa in Nsukka L.G.A and 200 respondents were each selected from each community making the total number of respondents 600.

Data Processing and Analysis:

Data editing and validation were done immediately on the field and upon return from the field. This helped to ensure that specific errors were detected and corrected. The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. The analysis of the information collected from the questionnaire was done using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency distribution, construction of tables and percentages. In order for the researcher to draw inference about the relationship between variables in the research work, the chi-square was used to test the hypotheses. Note that the tables were not included in due to page limitation.

Results and Discussion:

The study used 600 respondents. . Data on sex of respondents on shows that 340(56.7%) were males while 260(43.3%) were females. It can be observed that greater percent (56.7%) of the respondents were males. Wardle et. al. (2004) found that men are always moved by taste and are indulgence-focused while women are more influenced by health-related food marketing. This may be the major reason males were recorded as the greater percentage of the youth population influenced highly by food marketing in this study. Age of respondents show that 410(68.4%) were aged 18-27 years, 105(17.5%) were aged 28-37 years old, 65(10.8%) were aged 38-47

years, and 20(3.3%) were aged 48 years and above. It can be seen that greater percent (68.4%) of the respondents were between 18-27 years old. 80(13.3%) of the respondents were married, 500(83.3%) were single, while 20(3.4%) were widowed. It can be noted that majority (83.3%) of the respondents were single. Lusk and Briggeman (2009) found that married individuals tend to value food safety, nutrition, and price more than singles who may value taste and convenience more. It may then be why this study recorded a greater number and percentage of singles. Data on respondents' level of education shows that 404(67.3%) have finished secondary school education and 196(32.7%) have graduated from tertiary institution. This implies that majority (67.3%) of the respondents have completed secondary school education. It is known from various researches that higher-educated consumers tend to be more health-conscious. A study by Wardle, et.al. (2000) found that educational attainment was strongly associated with healthy food choices. On the other hand, lower-educated consumers rely more on price and advertising. Worsley (2002) found that nutrition knowledge which is often linked to educational level positively influenced food behaviour. This study recorded that lesser percentage of respondents (32.7%) attained tertiary level of education. This may be the major reason this study recorded high level of reliance on price and advertising and seeming poor knowledge of nutrition. Findings show that 300(50%) of the respondents earn less than ₦50,000 monthly, 128(21.3%) earn between ₦51,000-100,000 monthly, 102(17%) earn between ₦101,000-150,000 monthly, 60(10%) earn between ₦151,000-200,000, and 10(1.7%) earn ₦201,000 and above monthly. It can be noted that greater percent (50%) of the respondents earn less than ₦50,000 monthly income. Income as it is especially in this recent economic situation in Nigeria plays a critical role in shaping both food marketing strategies and consumer behaviour. Drewnowski and Specter (2004) on "poverty and obesity" found that low-incomers often choose high-calorie, energy-dense foods (fast food, processed snacks) because they are cheaper. On the other hand, higher-incomers may opt for organic foods due to greater health awareness and they can also afford those (Zepeda & Li, 2007). A critical assessment on the study result(s) show that greater percentage of the study respondents (50%) can be considered as low-incomers and further assessment on the study results shows that the outcome skewed to the direction of low-incomers consumer behaviour. Social media status of respondents shows that 406(67.6%) of the respondents are active social media users, 154(25.7%) are moderate social media users, while 40(6.7%) do not use social media. It can be noted that greater percent (67.6%) of the respondents are active social media users. Active social media presence by Nsukka LGA youth may not be over emphasized because most of them have smart phones and have a high priority sense of data acquisition and management inspite of the economic situation.

On the substantive findings; 104(17.3%) of the respondents said that food marketing is persuading consumers to buy food products and services, 230(38.4%) expressed that it is online and offline business promotion activities to create awareness of food products to sway consumer behaviour, 200(33.3%) answered it is advertisement of food products by food companies through traditional and digital channels, while 66(11%) viewed the aforementioned answers as their understanding of food marketing. The finding suggested that greater percent (38.4%) of the respondents understood food marketing as online and offline business promotion activities to create awareness of food products; used to sway consumer behaviour. On whether food marketing influences

consumers' behaviour; 422(70.3%) of the respondents affirmed that it does while 108(18%) said no, and 70(11.7%) said they do not know. It can be gathered that majority (70.3%) of the participants affirmed that food marketing influences consumers' behaviour. Findings on the extent of agreement on influence of food marketing on consumers' behaviour; shows that 505(84.2%) of the respondents agreed that food marketing influences consumers' behaviours while 95(15.8%) disagreed. It can be noted that majority (84.2%) of the respondents agreed that food marketing influences consumers' behaviour. Findings on respondents' views on the most influential medium of food marketing shows outdoor billboard 203(33.8%) television and radio 107(17.8%) social media platforms 270(45%), and media 20(3.4%). It can be noted that greater percent (45%) mentioned social media platforms as the most influential medium of food marketing. Result reveals that 370(61.7%) of the respondents' admitted that their decisions to purchase of food products are influenced by food marketing while 230(38.3%) of the respondents said they are not influenced. This means that majority (61.7%) of the respondents are influenced by food marketing in their decisions to purchase food products. This is to show how influential food marketing is at decision making for food purchase. The finding aligns with that of Boyland et. al. (2024), which found that exposure to food marketing is associated with increased food purchasing and consumption among adults. It also aligns with that of Kalog et. al. (2022) on their study on a large number of students found out that majority were highly influenced by food advertisements in their decision on food products. Aside the fact that majority of the respondents admitted that their decision to purchase food products stemmed from mode of food marketing; findings on factors that most influence respondents' decisions to purchase food products show that price 301(50.2%) was the major factor of influence; followed by, brand reputation 105(17.5%), packaging and labeling 94(15.7%), nutritional content 50(8.3%), celebrity endorsement 35(5.8%), and recommendations from friends and family 15(2.5%). This finding agreed with the findings of Melovic et. al. (2020) which found that price and promotion have the strongest impact on consumer acceptance and buying decisions. Findings on marketing strategies that influences respondents' decisions make purchase food products; shows the following marketing strategies that influence purchasing behaviour from consumers: use of jingles in TV/radio commercials 110(18.4%) product sampling and trials 90(15%), loyalty programmes and rewards 100(16.7%), discount sales 290(48.3%), celebrity influencing 8(1.3%), and testimonies by friends and families 2(0.3%). It can be gathered that greater percent (48.3%) of the respondents revealed that discount sale strategy by food marketers draw them to make food purchases. On the purchase of junk foods; 420(70%) of the respondents' said "yes" to food marketing influencing their purchase of junk food while 180(30%) of the respondents said they are not influenced. Out of the 370(61.7%) respondents that are influenced by food marketing, 210(56.8%) pay attention to food advertising on daily basis, 118(31.9%) pay attention 2-3 times a week, and 42(11.4%) pay attention once a week. It can be seen that greater percent (56.8%) of the respondents' attention to food marketing is on a daily basis. This finding aligns with that of Boyland et. al. (2024) and Kalog et. al. (2022) mentioned earlier. Paying attention to the result(s); one will find out that a great number (210) (highest percentage [56.8%]) pay attention to food marketing on a daily basis leading to exposure and increased food purchasing. Findings on measures to protect consumers' rights and wellbeing shows that 206(34.3%) of the respondents suggested regulation of food

companies to ensure compliance to best food marketing practices, 304(50.7%) proposed sanctions on food companies that violate consumers' rights and health, and 90(15%) proffered policies to ensure food products are of mandatory healthy nutritional level. It can be observed that greater percent (50.7%) of the respondents suggested regulation of food companies to ensure compliance to best food marketing practices as a measure to protect consumers' rights and wellbeing. Harris et. al. (2009) and also Cairns et. al. (2013) amongst others; highlighted how significant influence of food marketing is on consumer behaviour and they proposed some regulations be put forward on unhealthy food products.

The study hypothesized and adopted that: (a) male consumers are more likely to be influenced by food marketing than their female counterparts; (b) people who are active on social media are more likely to be influenced by food marketing than those who are not active; and (c) younger youth (18yrs-30yrs) are more likely to be influenced by food marketing than older youth (31yrs-48yrs).

Conclusion:

It can be concluded that food marketing plays a pivotal role in shaping consumer behaviour, influencing not only what individuals (the youth) choose to eat but also how they perceive food products and brands. Though various strategies such as advertising, packaging, pricing, and promotional tactics, marketers create appealing narratives that often affect purchasing decisions, especially among vulnerable groups like the youth owing to the major fact that most of them are low-incomers. This research applied a sociological perspective by showing that consumer behaviour is not merely a reflection of personal preferences but is significantly guided by external marketing stimuli. Understanding this dynamic is essential for both marketers aiming for effective strategies and policymakers seeking to promote healthier and more informed consumer choices. Future research and interventions should focus on ethical marketing practices and consumer education to foster a more balanced and health-conscious food environment.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- Nigerian government and lawmakers should establish and enforce regulations to restrict the marketing of unhealthy food products, particularly to vulnerable populations such as children and adolescents.
- Public health practitioners should design and implement education and awareness campaigns to empower consumers to make informed food choices and promote healthy eating habits.
- Food manufacturers should be required to provide clear and accurate labeling of food products, including nutritional content and ingredients, to enable consumers to make informed decisions.

Regulatory agencies should regularly monitor and evaluate food marketing strategies to ensure compliance with regulations and to identify areas for improvement.

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